

Interview Guide: The Provider

This guide will be used to interview providers following the visit for contraceptive counseling in which a patient used the decision aid app was provided to the patient to work through and bring to the visit. The provider also had access to the decision aid prior to the visit.

Notes for the research assistant: Introduce yourself and your role in the study to the interviewee. Provide information about yourself so that the interviewee understands how your background may or may not be relevant to the interview.

For each of the following questions, use the numbered questions to guide the interview and use the bulleted questions as probes if needed. Once each of the bulleted points has been addressed (either because interviewee offered it up or you have asked the probe), move on to the next numbered question. If an interviewee answers one of the numbered questions while answering another numbered question, there is no need to repeat the question.

Please record the interview and ensure that voices can be clearly heard on the recording.

Questions

Thank you for meeting. I will be asking you a series of questions about today's clinical encounter in which you and the patient discussed contraceptive options and during which a decision aid was used in some way.

1. Prior to the visit, your patient was asked to use a contraceptive decision aid in preparation for this visit.

- Have any of your patients ever utilized a tool like the one that was used during this visit? If yes, would you say fewer than 3 patients, 4-10 patients, or more than 10 patients?

This question identifies the provider's previous experience with shared decision making and decision aids, in order to put the interview in context. Because the research question asks if the decision aid "facilitates" shared decision making, we need to know how familiar the provider may be with this construct.

2. How do you feel the use of the decision aid impacted/influenced your discussion of contraceptive options?

- **What were some of the limitations or problems with using the decision aid to discuss contraceptive options?**

These are open-ended questions to elicit the provider's feelings about the encounter overall and sets the stage for more probing questions about the experiences of the provider in using shared decision making.

2. How did the decision aid change (if at all) what you would describe as your typical contraceptive counseling encounter?

These are open-ended questions to elicit the provider's feelings about the encounter overall and sets the stage for more probing questions about the experiences of the provider in using shared decision making.

3. How did the decision aid impact your overall ability to discuss the range of contraceptive options?

- **How did the decision aid impact your ability to discuss the benefits and risks of individual contraceptive options?**
- **How did the decision aid impact your ability to discuss individual contraceptive options in relation to the patient's individual situation/risk factors/preferences?**

This question addresses the part of the research question about the provider's perceived ability to communicate contraceptive options.

4. What did you perceive were your patient's feelings about the decision aid?

- **How familiar did she seem to be with the information on the decision aid?**
- **What questions or comments did she have or share that you felt were related to having read the decision aid ahead of time (or working through it together in the visit)?**
- **Did she provide any feedback about the decision aid (solicited or unsolicited)?**

This question does not directly address a specific objective of the study, but addresses an issue that providers often bring up as obstacles to the use of clinical support tools – i.e., “the patient doesn't like it.” The answer from the provider can be compared to the analogous answer from the patient.

5. What personal values or experiences did the patient mention during the encounter that you think impacted her contraceptive choice?

This question gets at actually identifying whether or not the provider was actually able to elicit patient values (part of the research question about whether the decision aid facilitates the provider's ability to elicit values of the patient).

6. What military-relevant concerns or issues did the patient mention during the encounter that you think influenced her ultimate contraceptive choice?

- For example, did the patient voice any concerns related to a contraceptive option that were related to her assigned duties in the military?

This question gets at actually identifying whether or not the provider was actually able to elicit military-relevant patient values.

7. What non-contraceptive benefits (if any) of one or more of the contraceptive options did you mention or highlight in the encounter?

- Were any of these relevant to the patient's role in the military?**
- Were any of these related to possible deployment?**

This question further explores whether or not the provider was actually able to elicit military-relevant patient preferences.

8. Did the patient seem comfortable making a decision about her contraceptive choice?

- Did her preferences change during the visit? If so, how?**
- If her preferences changed during the visit, what about the encounter seemed to influence that change?**
- What do you believe was/were the most important factor(s) in making her choice?**

This question gets at the provider's perception of the patient's agency in the decision-making process and therefore addresses the perceived effectiveness of the tool in enhancing patient agency.

9. How did you feel about allowing your patient to make the ultimate decision about her choice?

This question gets at the provider's feelings about encouraging patient's agency in the decision-making process and therefore addresses the perceived effectiveness of the tool in enhancing patient agency.

10. As a provider within the Military Health System, in the context of ensuring military readiness, what do you think is the role of shared decision making?

This question gets at the provider's feelings about the role of the provider community (and the MHS at large) in providing patient-centered care, while still ensuring readiness.

11. Is there training you would like in shared decision making and how to most effectively implement a decision aid in your practice?

This question addresses any desired education and training based on the provider's perspective.

12. What do you think of this decision aid overall?

- **What would you change about it?**
- **Would you use it again in the future? If yes, are there any patients for whom you think this decision aid would not be appropriate?**
- **If you would not use it again in the future, how would you conduct your contraceptive counseling?**
- **Did you feel constrained by the decision aid? If so, how?**

This final open-ended question provides the interviewee an opportunity to share any additional thoughts about the decision aid and indirectly about shared decision making. Based on the answers to this question, the decision aid could be modified in the future if similar themes emerge from the answers to this question.

13. Do you have any last comments and/or questions about today's questions or the app that you would like to share?